

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO THE STUDENTS WITH SPEECH IMPEDIMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article gives useful recommendations and tips for working with students who have speech defects. You can learn how to behave in front of students and how to increase their confidence.

To commence with, teaching is one of the responsible duty and working with people who have learning disabilities requires as twice as much effort on account of not having enough ability and discomfort while expressing ideas. These kind of learners feel difficulties while putting words to the correct order in a sentence. This problem occurs not only in nonnative languages but also in the native language, therefore teachers come across with enormous obstacle while teaching foreign languages.

As we know, students that have speech impediments are other-worldly and getting them down are unchallenging for a lack of confidence for that teachers must be careful and assiduous. When you are in class, be attentive and pay attention that your language is clear, because the class see what you are saying and read your lips if necessary. Use gestures to support and before asking say the student's name before

asking in order to recruit attention. Then always prepare yourself for giving instructions repeatedly because learners may ask again and again for clarification.

Working with pictures, objects and photos to help understand and remember new vocabulary visually. Phonemes and sounds build block for learners with speech impediments. At that time we must console with speech language pathologists and work multisensory activities such as electron stories or dictionaries with sound. When learner listens how to pronounce correctly, it will be useful and stucked to memory, then next time he/she can pronounce without challenges. Never be strict in the class, this leads students to frustration and they cannot say what they want and plan in their minds. Instead of this, stand near students when giving the instructions and ask the learners to repeat the directions.

The most effective way is using realias when your student has a speech defect. But when you show objects, try to pronounce correctly, because your student learn the way of saying words as you pronounced. Always encourage students and never cut off when they are speaking. It blocks learner and loose ideas and can not connect ideas. When you feel your student is uncontious, say him/her to breathe deeply and say to speak slowly but try it clearly.

At the end of the article i want to give a game instruction for speech impediment and it is

considered useful and you can understand it is helpful when you use it in the class. Whistle is required for this game and you distribute whistles for all group, then say some words in front of the class and you have to add some mistakes while pronouncing. If learner perceive your mistake, he/she must use whistle. Game lasts like that. You can use balls or claps if you are not able to find enough whistle for all group member.

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